

Kinetics and mechanism of electron transfer reactions of aquo-thallium(III) perchlorate with aldopentoses

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The kinetics of electron transfer reactions of aquo-thallium(III) perchlorate with D-xylose, D-arabinose and D-ribose have been studied under the pseudo-first order condition. The fractional order with respect to aldopentose concentrations suggest the Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics. The rate decreases with acid concentration, and is strongly inhibited by the complexing chloride, acetate ions and acetic acid. A free radical mechanism involving aldopentose derived free radical has proposed for these reactions. Rate law consistent with the experimental data has been also derived.

The electron transfer reactions of various metal ions with reducing sugars follow different types of mechanistic pathways elaborated by kinetic and other approaches¹. Further, the other aspects of carbohydrate chemistry particularly analytical deserve mention². Earlier the electron transfer reactions of aquo-thallium(III) perchlorate with hexoses, alditols and disaccharides have been studied kinetically³. Now the results of the kinetic study of the electron transfer reactions of aquo-thallium(III) perchlorate with aldopentoses (D-xylose, D-arabinose and D-ribose) are reported.

Results and Discussion

The rate data of these reactions have been obtained in the form of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) under the varying kinetic conditions. The disappearance of thallium(III) monitored iodometrically in the presence of excess concentrations of aldopentoses and perchloric acid followed first order kinetics uniformly upto at least two half-lives. The first order kinetics in these reactions has been justified by the calculation of k_{obs} by R/R method⁴ and also by applying regression analysis⁵ in the typical kinetic runs. The values of k_{obs} at different initial concentrations of thallium(III), aldopentoses and perchloric acid are given in Table 1. The observed slight increase in k_{obs} with initial concentrations of thallium(III) can tentatively be attributed to the slight increase in the initial concentrations of the reactive species of thallium(III) formed in the present reaction conditions. The fractional slope values found in the aldopentose concentration variations indicated the possibility of Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics in these reactions. The observed negative slope values (~ -1.0) in the perchloric acid variations were further confirmed by observing the similar trend when hydrogen ion concentration was varied

at constant perchlorate ion (Table 2). Increase in rate constant with perchlorate ion (ionic strength) (Table 2) and a sharp decrease in rate with complexing acetate and chloride ions were also obtained in these studies (Table 3).

Table 1 Variation of k_{obs} with initial thallium(III), aldopentose and perchloric acid concentrations

Temp = 318 K					
$10^2 [Tl^{III}]$	$10 [Aldopentose]$	$10 [HClO_4]$	$10^5 k_{obs} (s^{-1})$		
mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	D-Xylose	D-Arabinose	D-Ribose
0.5 ^a	5.0	7.40	8.93	11.99	25.17
1.0 ^a	5.0	7.40	9.00	12.99	28.24
2.0 ^a	5.0	7.40	9.78	13.60	30.02
3.0 ^a	5.0	7.40	11.58	14.36	32.57
1.0	1.0	7.94	1.12	2.65	9.00
1.0	3.0	7.94	2.42	7.28	18.03
1.0	5.0	7.94	3.75	10.87	26.40
1.0	7.0	7.94	4.76	14.03	37.30
1.0	9.0	7.94	5.77	16.23	45.22
1.0	5.0	4.94	5.52	17.63	40.23
1.0	5.0	7.94	3.75	10.87	20.96
1.0	5.0	10.94	3.02	8.08	18.53
1.0	5.0	13.94	2.33	6.00	14.85
1.0	5.0	16.94	2.02	5.02	11.37
Slope of log k_{obs} and log [Aldopentose]			0.42	0.83	0.76
Slope of log k_{obs} and log [HClO ₄]			-1.14	-1.02	-1.02

^aTemp = 323 K

However, the order with respect to D-xylose concentrations in the presence of complexing acetic acid has been found to be unity. The second order rate constants ($k_o = k_{obs} [D\text{-xylose}]$) decreased from 8.36×10^{-5} to 3.76×10^{-5} mol⁻¹ dm³ s⁻¹ with the increase in the concentration of complexing acetic acid from 0– 10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ at the constant concentrations of all the reacting species. From the temperature variation data, ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were computed as 53.93–106.72 kJ mol⁻¹ and $-(10.13\text{--}49.14)$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, respectively. The stoichiometric reactions under the kinetic

run conditions and in the presence of excess (~20-folds) concentrations of thallium(III) are presented in eqns. (1) and (2), respectively, for all the three aldopentoses,

Formic acid was confirmed qualitatively and also quantitatively to propose 1 : 1 stoichiometry for these reactions under the kinetic run conditions (eqn. 1). Formaldehyde along with formic acid were confirmed as intermediate products in the stoichiometric studies carried out in the presence of excess concentration of thallium(III) (eqn. 2).

Table 2. Variation of k_{obs} with hydrogen and perchlorate ion concentrations

$10^2 [Tl^{III}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10 [\text{Aldopentose}] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$					
$10[H^+]$	$10[ClO_4^-]$	$10[\mu]$	$10^5 k_{obs} (s^{-1})$		
mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	D-Xylose	D-Arabinose	D-Ribose
Temp. = 318 K					
4.94	16.94	0.12	7.32	20.12	46.13
7.94	16.94	0.12	5.19	12.93	28.03
10.94	16.94	0.12	4.01	10.02	19.18
13.94	16.94	0.12	3.05	7.32	15.15
16.94	16.94	0.12	1.92	5.02	11.37
Temp. = 323 K					
7.65	7.65	0.82	7.21	19.93	37.30
7.65	8.65	0.92	9.23	23.31	41.05
7.65	9.65	1.02	11.02	24.82	45.32
7.65	11.65	1.22	14.25	29.03	48.81
Slope of log k_{obs} and log $[H^+]$			-1.17	-1.09	-1.13
Slope of log k_{obs} and $[\mu]^{1/2}$			0.39	0.37	0.27

Table 3. Variation of k_{obs} with chloride and acetate ion concentrations*

$10^2 [Tl^{III}] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10 [\text{Aldopentose}] = 5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10 [HClO_4] = 7.65 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10 [\mu] = (a) 8.55, (b) 0.94 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 323 K							
$10^3 [Cl^-]$	$10^5 k_{obs}(s^{-1})$			$10^2 [CH_3COO^-]$	$10^5 k_{obs}(s^{-1})$		
	(A)	(B)	(C)		(A)	(B)	(C)
0	7.21	19.93	37.30	0	7.21	19.93	37.30
2.5	3.70	10.32	18.58	2.5	4.37	16.80	24.03
7.5	1.85	6.03	10.38	7.5	2.51	11.32	15.09
15.0	1.02	3.85	5.81	15.0	1.92	6.83	9.32
30.0	0.44	1.05	3.02	30.0	1.20	3.10	5.71
Slope of log k_{obs} and log $[Cl^-]$			Slope of log k_{obs} and log $[CH_3COO^-]$				
-0.78 -0.78 -0.71			-0.54 -0.52 -0.54				

* (A) D-xylose, (B) D-arabinose, (C) D-ribose.

Formation of intermediate free radicals was confirmed by the induced polymerization reaction with acryl nitrile in these studies. This observation is consistent with the reported spin-trapping of monosaccharide derived carbon centered free radicals during the photo and thermal red-ox reactions of monosaccharides including aldopentoses with metal ions⁶. The mechanistic steps of the electron transfer

reactions with thallium(III) involving organic substrates have been elaborated on the basis of different kinetic features observed in a particular reaction⁷. In the present reactions, the mechanistic steps essentially consist of the formation of first hydrolysed species of Tl^{3+} , $Tl(OH)^{2+}$ (eqn. 3) which reacted with free aldehyde form of the aldopentose to give an intermediate complex in the rapid equilibrium step (eqn. 4). This complex then disproportionated in a slow rate-determining step involving water as proton transferring agent (Bunnett parameter (w) > 3.3; Table 2) to give a carbon centered free radical, formic acid and a transient thallium(II) species (eqn. 5). The transient free radical and thallium(II) then reacted in a fast step to produce lower monosaccharide which was ultimately converted to carbon dioxide in the presence of excess concentration of thallium(III) by a free radical mechanism (eqns. 6 and 2),

where, R^\bullet is free radical $(CH_2OH(CHOH)_2\bullet CHOH)$

(lower monosaccharide)

The formation of $Tl(OH)^{2+}$ as reactive species of thallium(III) is supported by the inverse dependence of rate on hydrogen ion and increase in rate with perchlorate ion concentrations (ionic strength) (Table 2). A strong retardation in rate due to chloride and acetates can be attributed to the removal of this active species due to the formation of strong covalent complexes like $(Tl(OH)Cl)^+$ and $(Tl(OH)Ac)^{6+}$ (Table 3).

The observed first order dependence on D-xylose concentration in the presence of complexing acetic acid and the observed decrease in rate with acetic acid concentration can be explained by considering the formation of complexed acetate species with unhydrolysed thallium(III) as shown in eqn. 7,

The unhydrolysed thallium(III) then reacts with D-xylose in a similar way as in eqns. (5) and (6) with a difference that the electron transfer takes place in the transition state as there is no kinetic evidence of the complex formation between thallium(III) and D-xylose in the presence of complexing acetic acid.

However, in the absence of any complexing species, the observed Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics (Table 1) clearly provide a kinetic evidence of complex formation between thallium(III) and aldopentose in the pre-equilibrium step (eqn. 4). This is further supported spectrophotometri-

cally at room temperature (25°) where the disproportionation rate (eqn. 5) of the complex formed is almost negligible. The results of the Job's method of continued variation indicate the formation of 1 : 1 complex in these reactions,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{dt} = \frac{k K K_{\text{h}} [\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5] [\text{H}^+]^{-1}}{1 + K_{\text{h}} [\text{H}^+]^{-1} + K K_{\text{h}} [\text{C}_5\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_5] [\text{H}^+]^{-1}} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} \quad (8)$$

The derived rate law (eqn. 8) has been validated by evaluating the values of equilibrium constant of the complex formation (K) and the rate of its disproportionation (k) from the linear plots obtained between $(k_{\text{obs}})^{-1}$ and $[\text{aldopentose}]^{-1}$ using the rate data (Table 1) and the calculated value of hydrolysis constant (eqn. 3) ($K_{\text{h}} = 0.50 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) at 318 K from the reported values of K_{h} ⁸ and enthalpy of hydrolysis⁹ in the literature. The values of K thus calculated are 3.81, 3.15 and 3.44 and that of k are 1.01×10^{-4} , 5.00×10^{-4} and $6.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively, for D-xylose, D-arabinose and D-ribose reactions.

Equation(7) and other equations similar to eqns. (5) and (6) can be used to obtain the following rate law for the reaction of D-xylose with thallium(III) in the presence of acetic acid,

$$-\frac{d [\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{dt} = \frac{k [\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{D-xylose}]}{1 + K_{\text{e}} [\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}] [\text{H}^+]^{-1}} = k_{\text{o}} [\text{Tl}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{D-xylose}]$$

where k_{o} is the second order rate constant ($k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{D-xylose}]$).

The equilibrium constant of the complex formation between thallium(III) and acetic acid (eqn. 7) has been computed as 9.46 from the linear plot between (k/k_{o}) and (acetic acid) using rate data.

Thus, these mechanistic steps (eqns. 3–6) and the derived rate law (eqn. 8) explain kinetic results obtained in the present study.

Experimental

The kinetic and other experimental details are the same

as described earlier³. Check experiments were performed to observe liberation of iodine only by the unused thallium(III) in the reaction mixture used in the kinetic runs and not by any other reagent present in the reaction mixtures.

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References

1. R. P. Bhatnagar and A. G. Fadnis, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1986, **45**, 90. K. K. Sengupta and S. N. Basu in "Topics in Chemistry. Series 1. Chemical Kinetics and Reaction Mechanism", ed K. S. Gupta. RBSA, Jaipur, 1992.
2. M. S. P. Rao, T. S. Rao, K. A. Rao and S. R. Sagi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 149; H. S. Singh, G. R. Verma, A. Gupta and A. Mittal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 392.
3. A. G. Fadnis and S. K. Shrivastava, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1982, **102**, 23; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 147; *Cienc. Cult. (Sao Paulo)*, 1981, **33**, 1335; *An. Quim.*, 1986, **82**, 5; A. G. Fadnis, *Oxid. Commun.*, 1985/86, **8**, 193; A. G. Fadnis and N. Bhatnagar, *Oxid. Commun.*, 1993, **16**, 244; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 669; S. N. Shukla and R. N. Kesarwani, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1984, **133**, 319; S. N. Shukla, R. N. Kesarwani and S. Taqi, *Oxid. Commun.*, 1984, **7**, 369; S. Arzare, M. Dave-Gautam and A. G. Fadnis, *Nat. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, 1997, **20**, 10; *Samyak J. Chem.*, 1997, **1**, 26; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 423.
4. D. Borderie, D. Lavabra, G. Levy and J. C. Macheau, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1990, **67**, 459.
5. H. S. Tan and W. E. Jones, *J. Chem. Educat.*, 1989, **66**, 650.
6. A. G. Fadnis, *Oxid. Commun.*, 1990, **13**, 41; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 1.
7. K. S. Gupta and Y. K. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 1285; K. S. Gupta, D. Kumar, R. Bhargava, A. Rani and D. S. N. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 619.
8. T. E. Rogers and G. M. Waind, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1961, **57**, 1360.
9. Yu. B. Yokolev, F. Ya. Kulba and L. N. Thu, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1967, **41**, 1168.